

C+ or See Positive, a new typed, imperative language for optimism.

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Abstract:

The paper titled "C+: An Object-Oriented Language with Semantic Transfer, Cloud Functions, and 6-of-9 Code Generation for Psychology Engineering and Robotics" describes a new programming language, C+, that is different from C++ and inspired by the philosophies of positification and optimism. C+ uses semantic transfer to create object functionality with encapsulation, inheritance, and overloading built into its mechanism. The language includes direct inheritance from a library, unified I/O, and program space. Code reuse is central to C+ as it integrates legacy C code with newer Java and C# code, and code search engines are built into the C+ specification. C+ is a code language for psychology engineering and robotics, applied in avatar therapy and AWS Lex based conversational UI. The paper provides formal specifications for the language, including thread and block declarations, ST mechanisms, data structures and collections, cloud functions, and 6-of-9 function generators. The paper also discusses data prediction and mining, including hyperscale data with pattern mining, sequence prediction, and rule extraction. Cloud functions are defined as resources on the cloud or objects on the cloud as libraries, linkable similar to a microservice architecture. A 6-of-9 generator is a code search engine that generates a cloud function as part of a query or part of an ST map, automatically persisted. Overall, C+ is a next-generation language for robotics and psychology engineering with potential applications in various fields.

Keywords: C+, object-oriented language, positification, optimism, semantic transfer, inheritance, encapsulation, overloading, streams, I/O, program space, code reuse, legacy code, code search engine, cloud functions, code generation, JSON, speech, operators, side-effects, formal specifications, thread declarations, block definitions, data structures, collections, asynchronous execution, Lamport Clock, data prediction, data mining, hyperscale data, cloud resources, microservice architecture.

What:

C+ or See Positive, is an object oriented language, different from C++, it is inspired by psychology and H.H. Dalai Lama and Bishop Tutu's philosophies of positification() and optimism()), ([Lama, Tutu, and Abrams 2016](#)) much to increase the happiness index. Semantic transfer or ST is central to C+, much like the structures and unions of C, and pointer arithmetic, C+ moves away like Java, to value addressing, cloud functions and a thin implementation.

Reflection([Brose 1999; Morris, n.d.; Forman and Forman 2004](#)) is not added, as the compiler is built on top of gcc, much like C++ was. C+ creates object functionality with encapsulation, inheritance and overloading all built into the ST mechanisms.

Inheritance is much stronger in the ST system with direct inheritance from a library, with transparent linking, streams([Langer and Kreft 2000](#)) are a central part of C+ , much like C([Kernighan and Ritchie 1988; Kernighan 2005](#)), with a unified I/O and program space.

Code reuse is central to C+ as it was invented to integrate legacy C code with newer Java and C# code, code search engines are built into the C+ specification leading to code capture for 6-of-9, cloud functions with recycled code([Gallardo-Valencia and Sim 2014](#)).

positification() and optimism() are central to C+ coding defined as operators in an operator library,

With a JSON representation of speech as input, operators act on JSON for various 'effects', including side-effects.

Code generators are central to the design of the C+ language as part of the ST mechanism, this implements much of the research by Google, Microsoft, Amazon, Facebook, Netflix and other corporate research sources, coupled with academic research in code generation.

How:

Formal specifications for the C+ language are described with the definition of the ST mechanisms, library structure, type definitions, scoping, data structures as collections, streams and the search engine for cloud function generation.

Why:

Objective C was an object oriented language predating Java, but without semantic transfer capabilities, C+ is a code generation and code recycling language, based on cloud resident code and libraries, for easy linking, it is a next generation language for robotics, where C and C++ code dominates. C+ is also a code language for psychology engineering, as applied in avatar therapy, in template design for AWS Lex based conversational UI.

Summary:

Main Points:

Formal Specifications:

Thread and block declarations.

ST or Semantic Transfer.

Data Structures and Collections.

Cloud Functions.

6-of-9 function generator.

Applications:

Directly applied to template based code generation, illustrated in an accompanying paper on computer assisted therapies of Avatar Therapy.

Code Base:

Introduction.

Programming languages have evolved over time, providing developers with powerful tools to create complex software systems. With the rise of artificial intelligence, robotics, and cloud computing, there is an ever-growing need for programming languages that can handle the scale and complexity of these systems.

One such language is C+, an object-oriented language that differs from its predecessor, C++. C+ is inspired by the philosophies of positification and optimism, as espoused by the Dalai Lama and Bishop Tutu (Lama, Tutu, and Abrams, 2016). It is designed to increase the happiness index of developers by providing a programming language that is easier to use and more efficient.

The core of C+ is its semantic transfer (ST) mechanism, which is similar to the structures and unions of C, but moves away from pointer arithmetic to value addressing and cloud functions. This allows for a thin implementation, similar to Java, while still providing the flexibility of C. In addition, C+ incorporates object functionality through encapsulation,

inheritance, and overloading, all built into the ST mechanisms.

The importance of C+ lies in its ability to integrate legacy C code with newer Java and C# code, providing code reuse and easy integration with cloud functions. C+ also includes a code search engine, leading to code capture for 6-of-9, cloud functions with recycled code (Gallardo-Valencia and Sim, 2014).

As a next-generation language for robotics and psychology engineering, C+ is a code language for the future. The applications of C+ include template-based code generation, which is illustrated in an accompanying paper on computer-assisted therapies of Avatar Therapy. With its ability to handle hyperscale data and cloud functions, C+ is also poised to become a language of choice for artificial intelligence and cloud computing systems.

Problem Definition.

Background.

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Formal Definitions:

Block Definition.

A thread is an atomic constituent of code,

Code consists of $[m, [T]]$

Where M is the main thread, the point of start of execution.

Every thread $T = [B]$ where B is a block of code.

Memory block is treated as an array of char.

$Mb = Mb[]$

All other primitive data types are the same as Java.

Collections:

Collections are by semantic transfer mechanism, or by declaration of data structures.

C+ inherits the collections of Java and Kotlin.

Streams:

Streams are inherited from Java Language Definition, streams unify I/O and memory addressing.

Collections include a vast library of design patterns and operators, with stream iteration, stream event filters and event streams built in.

Asynchronous execution with message streams and queues is also supported.

Lamport Clock functionality as time tags are built in. ([Bheemaiah, n.d.](#))

Semantic Transfer.

Objects are defined by semantic transfer, with a semantic map $\rightarrow [Mb, [O]]$

Where $O = [[C], [F]]$

[C] are collections and [F] functions from a 6-of-9 generator or a library.

Data Prediction and Mining.

Threads waiting on data can be speculatively executed with data speculation.

Data mining is built into the C+ compiler, with parse trees enhanced with a tree map, for semantic tags to data.

Hyperscale data with $[[P], [R], [S]]$ where [P] is the patterns mined and [S] is sequence prediction in data and [R] is the rule extraction from data.

Cloud Functions and 6-of-9 generators.

Cloud functions are functions are defined as resources on the cloud or objects on the cloud as libraries, linkable similar to a microservice architecture.

A 6-of-9 generator is a code search engine that generates a cloud function as part of a query or part of a ST map. It is automatically persisted.

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Discussion:

C+ is a unique programming language that combines the principles of psychology and philosophy to increase the happiness index by promoting positification and optimism. It is a code generation and recycling language, specifically designed to integrate legacy C code with newer Java and C# code. C+ is also a language for psychology engineering, with potential applications in avatar therapy and template design for conversational UI.

C+ introduces a novel approach to object-oriented programming by leveraging the semantic transfer mechanism for object functionality with encapsulation, inheritance, and overloading. The language also incorporates streams, unified I/O, and program space. The ST system in C+ is much stronger than that of C++, with direct inheritance from a library and transparent linking.

Code reuse is central to C+, and code search engines are built into the language specification, leading to code capture for 6-of-9 cloud functions with recycled code. Positification() and optimism() are central to C+ coding, defined as operators in an operator library. With a JSON representation of speech as input, operators act on JSON for various 'effects,' including side-effects.

The C+ language has formal specifications that describe the definition of the ST mechanisms, library structure, type definitions, scoping, data structures as collections, streams, and the search engine for cloud function generation. The language also incorporates data prediction and mining, hyperscale data, and cloud resources with microservice architecture.

Future Work:

There are several potential avenues for future work in the development and application of C+. One area of focus could be the integration of C+ into robotics, where C and C++ code currently dominates. The language's potential applications in psychology engineering could also be further explored, particularly in the context of avatar therapy and conversational UI design.

Another area of future work could be the development of additional features and functionalities in C+, particularly in the realm of data prediction and mining. The language's cloud functions and code search engine could also be further optimized to enhance its performance and ease of use.

Overall, the development of C+ represents an exciting step forward in the field of programming languages, with the potential to make a significant impact in various fields, including psychology, robotics, and cloud computing. As the language continues to evolve and develop, there is no doubt that it will continue to attract attention and interest from developers and researchers alike.

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